

LETTER OF INTENT OF THE PARAGUAYAN GROUP

Dear members of the LASF4RI-HECAP initiative,

The experiments that the Paraguayan group are working in High Energy Physics are

- 1) CONNIE experiment
- 2) DUNE experiment
- 3) SBND experiment

Each of these experiments sent their plans and information by the Brazilian institutes: UFRJ for CONNIE, and UNICAMP for DUNE and SBND

In all the experiments we participate with electronic engineering since the only faculty that is involved in HEP projects are with the Engineering Faculty of the Universidad Nacional de Asuncion.

For CONNIE we help to the Fermilab electronics group in the development of the new CCD package that is being built now, and also in the data analysis, mainly using Artificial Intelligence in the analysis of the images took by the CCDs.

For DUNE we help to the ARAPUCA detector system in two items: i) Cold electronics for the amplification of the SiPM, and ii) in the communication of the DAPHNE module (in charge of the digitation of the signals) with the DAQ system.

For SBND we help in the integration of the ARAPUCA signals with the DAQ.

SPACE WEATHER

We also are starting to work with space weather, this is mostly due to the fact that Paraguay is exactly at the center of the South Atlantic Magnetic Anomaly. In that sense, I want to call the attention about this topic, that we consider must be a priority of the region since their implication to the society. We are referring to the measurement of the low energy cosmic rays, that we believe must be well monitor now that the magnetosphere is weakening.

We are in contact with the INPE (Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais) from Brazil that are helping us to install magnetometers in order to be part of the EMBRACE net that measures the magnetic field in South America.

We are now installing a new muon detector that will help measuring not only the flux, but the incoming direction as well. Also we will install neutron detectors in the future.

We are in a small Project call Escaramujo, that uses muon detectors read by SiPMs. They were installed in many countries in Central and South America, but is not being activated at the moment.